

FROM *LAÏCITÉ* TO *NATIONALISME LAÏCISTE*

ALEXIS ARTAUD DE LA FERRIÈRE¹

ABSTRACT: In recent decades, various state actors have sought to mobilize the nominal notions of “religion” and “religious freedom” to justify policies that have little to do with the principle of protecting the liberty of conscience or the free manifestation of religious belief, nor with the underlying values of particular religious traditions. Such actions signify a worrying international trend toward the instrumentalization of religious freedom for the purposes of repressing political dissent, promoting exclusionary forms of religious nationalism, and discriminating against minorities. French domestic politics are not exempt from this overarching trend, although the manner in which it is manifest in France is colored by that country’s specific demographic profile and its particular history of Church-State relations. At the heart of this French specificity (but certainly not a French exception) is the notion of *laïcité*, premised in art. 10 of the 1789 Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen, formalized in the 1905 law on the separation of the Churches and the State, and consecrated as a constitutional principle in article 1 of the 1946 Constitution and again in article 1 of the current 1958 Constitution.

KEYWORDS: *laïcité*, religious liberty, French law

Yves Gaudemet describes *laïcité* as “the French form of religious liberty”. That is to say that the regime of separation and non-recognition, introduced through art. 2 of the 1905 Law on the Churches and the States, is the means by which the Republic ensures liberty of conscience and the free exercise of worship (as stipulated in art. 1, under the sole restrictions enumerated within the subsequent articles of the law in the interest of public order). As the State Council noted in 2004, in a historical review of its own jurisprudence, the substantive principle of *laïcité* contains three key dimensions: 1) the neutrality of the state and of public servants with regards to all opinions and beliefs; 2) religious liberty, which cannot be reduced to State neutrality or toleration, but which implies equality between religious groups and the requirement to reconcile religious freedom with the respect

¹ Alexis Artaud de La Ferrière is Lecturer in Sociology at Royal Holloway College, University of London and Associate Researcher at the Groupe Sociétés Religions Laïcités (EPHE/CNRS) in Paris

for public order; 3) religious pluralism, such that all religions have the right to expression and that none may monopolize the State or undermine the fundamental principle on which rests the State.

Without strictly defining *laïcité*, this gloss provides a framework for understanding the pragmatic and liberal interpretation which had characterized the State Council's administrative rulings until 2004. This interpretation in keeping with the legislator's original intentions, as expressed by Aristide Briand, one of the key architects of the 1905 settlement: "Whenever the public interest cannot be legitimately invoked in the silence of the texts or in the doubt of their exact application, it is the liberal solution that will be most in conformity with legislative thought".

However, as Jean Bauberot and Micheline Milot have written, the political history of *laïcité* in France has always been torn between two competing tendencies. On the one hand, there exists a liberal tendency favoring state neutrality, freedom of conscience, and religious group autonomy as a necessary dimension of individual liberty; this position is largely inspired by the Lockean Anglo-American tradition. On the other hand, there also exists a Jacobin/Bonapartist tendency that favors state regulation of religion and limitations on the autonomy of religious groups with regards to their internal organization and public activities. Although anti-clerical in spirit and associated with the irreligious *libre pensée* movement, by virtue of the dominant position that this Jacobin/Bonapartist tendency prescribes for the State over religious groups, its heritage is also to be found in the Gallican tradition of the *Ancien Régime* that existed until 1789 and which allowed for significant intervention of the Crown within the affairs of the Catholic Church in France.

Until the adoption of the 2004 law on religious symbols in schools, this latter Jacobin/Bonapartist tendency was principally restricted to what Alessandro Ferrarri has called the sphere of "narrative *laïcité*". Although the Jacobin/Bonapartist tendency increasingly dominated the public discourse from the late 1980's, it found little expression in the legal regime of *laïcité*. Indeed, to the chagrin of more ardent secularists, the legislator passed numerous laws favorable to religious accommodations for religious expression, compromising in some respects the formal regime of separation; and these laws were consistently supported and liberally interpreted by the State Council. These included the law of 1907 which allows religious groups the free use of publicly owned religious buildings, the allocation of public funds in 1920 for the construction of the Paris Grand Mosque, a 1961 finance law that allows public authorities to guarantee loans granted to religious associations, and a 1987 law that allows

donors to deduct from their taxes a portion of the money given to churches (originally 40%, subsequently raised to 66%). Arguably, such accommodations have at times compromised a strict interpretation of separation of church and state. However, they found their justification in that they represented a liberal advance in favor of the free exercise of religion within the historical conditions of XXth century France.

However, since 2004, the Jacobin/Bonapartist tendency has steadily made headway in the legal realm. As stated above, this trend was ushered in by a ban on ostentatious religious symbols in public schools, but it was extended in 2010 with the passage of a law banning full-face coverings in public and in 2016 with the El Khomri labor law, which granted employers the right to restrict employees' manifestation of beliefs at work. This legislative trend has in turn constrained the ability of the Conseil d'Etat to deliver more liberal rulings in terms of religious liberty (as had historically been its orientation), because the council is bound by the express provisions of the law. Certain authors have described this recent trend as “*nouvelle laïcité*” or neo-*laïcité*. As Stéphanie Hennette-Vauchez and Vincent Valentin argue in *L'affaire Baby Loup ou la Nouvelle Laïcité*, a core position of this tendency is to oppose “the freedom to manifest one's religious beliefs in a public place or in certain private structures” on the basis that such manifestations are a violation of the principle of *laïcité*. However, as these authors point out, such a position runs counter to (indeed, it undermines) the legal principle of *laïcité* as it was forged, interpreted, and affirmed throughout the 20th century.

Thus, from a principle guaranteeing freedom of conscience and the free exercise of worship, proponents of neo-*laïcité* have derived the basis for new-found restrictions on religious freedom. Here we find the reflection of the inversion of meaning which others have identified in the political instrumentalization of the language of religious liberty, in the United States and elsewhere. Capitalizing on the discursive legitimacy of *laïcité*, and reviving a restrictive secularist interpretation of that notion (echoing the past positions of anti-clerical Socialists such as Maurice Allard and Edouard Vaillant) which was firmly rejected by the legislator in 1905 and in subsequent legislation, proponents of neo-*laïcité* mobilize this language to undermine the very principles of state neutrality, religious liberty, and religious pluralism, which the regime of separation was designed to uphold.

Indeed, as neo-*laïcité* has consolidated itself over the past two decades, it has taken on an increasingly normative and legalistic profile, such that we may now characterize it as a substantive doctrine which we might call “*nationalisme laïciste*” (a term sometimes applied to the Turkish Kemalist

regime) because of the formal characteristics that it shares with doctrines of religious nationalism observable in other contexts. What are these characteristics? First amongst these is the affirmation of the moral legitimacy of the nation and the political authority of the state in affirming and regulating that moral legitimacy. This idea is of course not restricted to religious nationalism: it broadly describes the notion of sovereignty as it is instantiated by all nation-states. However, the particularity of religious nationalism is that it uses this notion of sovereignty as a vehicle to promote its substantive normative agenda and to co-opt the coercive power of the state in restricting the groups freedoms of minorities which are perceived as subservice to the ideal of national unity. The second characteristic is a rejection (or at least a qualification) of the liberal political order, which is seen as being in crisis in at least three respects: 1) because it cannot maintain a cohesive sense of social meaning across autonomous self-defining individuals and fragmented cultural sub-groups; 2) because, in the absence of a cohesive sense of social meaning, it cannot sustain a unified popular commitment to the common good; 3) by extension, because it cannot maintain popular adhesion to the political legitimacy of the state. The third characteristic is the promotion of a normative system of ideas and ways of being as the substantive foundation for the nation's moral legitimacy and as a necessary reference of national unity to counter social fragmentation: civic belonging is predicated, according to this view, on cultural belonging. The fourth characteristic is the deployment of a strategy to promote a normative agenda in the political public sphere through the fielding of candidates for public office and the passage of laws: working through the institutions of State to gain influence over the direction of the course of the nation rather than receding from those institutions in an communitarian or quietest manner.

Nationalisme laïciste as we have described it shares these core characteristics with expressions of religious nationalism observable in other parts of the world. Though not religious in the sense of constituting a worldview based on a specific set of metaphysical beliefs, *nationalisme laïciste* does promote a substantive normative belief that citizens should not only fulfill certain civic obligations to the nation, but that they should believe in the moral goodness of the French Republican regime and publicly manifest their loyalty to that regime. Overt expressions of religious commitment or exogenous cultural affiliation are discouraged because they are perceived to undermine national cohesion and to qualify citizens' commitment to the nation. In practice, these efforts are primarily directed against popular expressions of Islam (and to a lesser extent Evangelical Christianity and

New Religious Movements), whilst more tolerance is accorded to Catholicism. However, it is important to note that insofar as *nationalisme laïciste* exempts Catholics from the brunt of its discursive attacks, this is because Catholicism is seen by this movement as being deeply rooted within the nation's history and traditions. Accommodations for Catholicism, on this view, are justified only to the extent that they serve and promote a culturally and morally substantive project of national unity; what is valued is the cultural heritage of Catholicism, not its doctrinal commitments or exterior manifestations of belief. Practicing Catholics, meanwhile, are legally subject to the same legal restrictions on religious liberty that since 2004 have increasingly constrained other religious denominations.

Undoubtedly, the most significant and wide-reaching incursion of *nationalisme laïciste* into French law to date has been the adoption of the 2021 Law reinforcing the respect of the principles of the Republic, which expresses many of the aforementioned formal features of religious nationalism. In its exposition of the motives underlying this law submitted to the National Assembly, the government under the Presidency of Emmanuel Macron explicitly identified the need to counter "the insidious and powerful communitarianism that is slowly eroding the foundations of French society" and to reinforce Republican principles in the face of those who "disrupt national cohesion and fraternity". In order to counter this supposed threat, the bill restricts freedoms of association and religion through a wide-ranging array of new surveillance measures, sanctions, and bureaucratic obligations. First, the bill furthers the displacement of the obligation of neutrality from the state and public servants to the individual citizen within public spaces and certain private spaces such as the workplace, notably by requiring new standards of neutrality for private contractors who fulfill public tenders (art. 1). Second, the bill makes it more difficult and costly to create religious associations and it restricts the internal autonomy of religious associations (art. 69, 74). Third, it increases legal penalties for crimes committed by ministers of religion or within a religious association or by individual members of a religious association (Art. 80-87). Fourth, the bill increases the regulatory obligations imposed on private schools, most of which are faith-based, and expedites the conditions of their administrative closure (art. 55). Fifth, it restricts parents' right to choose their children's education by banning home education, except subject to derogation which can only be accorded on the basis of one of four narrow criteria: the child's state of health or disability; the child's pursuit of intensive sports or artistic activities; itinerancy of the family; or a vague condition pertaining to the child's specific situation that

motivates the parents' educational project (art. 49). Finally, it aims to co-opt civil society and sporting associations in the active promotion of what the state identifies as Republican values, notably by obliging such associations to sign a "contract of republican commitment" (art. 12). For proponents of *nationalisme laïciste*, such new restrictions are justified in order to combat social fragmentation within the nation and to rally citizens around a normatively substantive ideal of the Republic that is not sufficiently well guarded by a liberal *laissez-faire* attitude with regards to religious groups.

Although the philosophical and political advocates of *laïcité* in France have always included currents of thought hostile to religious doctrines and to religious group autonomy, the legislative and jurisprudential approach to the application of the principle of *laïcité* since 1905 had historically provided an effective framework for the protection of freedom of religion. This situation has gradually shifted over the past twenty years as successive governments have succeeded in passing legislation limiting laws limiting individual religious liberties and the group autonomy of religious organizations, and increasingly displacing the burden of neutrality from the State to individuals. This legislative trend accompanies (and is sustained by) an increasingly dominant discursive trend within the public sphere that mobilizes the language of *laïcité* as an instrument hostile to individual religious conscience and public manifestations of religion. The political instrumentalization of *laïcité* as a new form of nationalism (fueled by anxieties related to social fragmentation, political disaffectation, terrorism, and clerical sexual abuse) is gaining a new intensity, threatening to disrupt the liberal balance which has held for over one hundred years.